

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.413 Max: 62.909	1385 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Natural <input type="checkbox"/> Anthropoc	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 1729-1730 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: *city layer beneath 1383*

Covered by SU: 1383 Fills SU: 1322 Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction

FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

SOIL/MATRIX: clay 85% silt 70% sand 5%

Granular Layered Cohesive

Compaction	Color
<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to: SU 1279 Is bound to (only for masonry):

Is abutted by: SU 1279 Abuts:

Is covered by: SU 1383 Covers: 1392, 1001

Is cut by:

Is filled by: Fills: 1322

OBSERVATIONS: *Δ412 altar base on eastern wall continuation of a wall was found northern portion of the SU is finds rich, including many largely in tact vessels - southern portion lacks it*

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: *Southern central section of Area B, due South of SU 1279.*

Shape: *Rectangular*

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): *Slope slightly towards the South, becomes a sharp slope at southern end.*

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): *Visible large rocks + some pottery + tiles.*

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): *Thickness decreases slightly to the south*

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:

Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

Description:

INTERPRETATION

SU served as drainage to the East of the house, over time wash off accumulation attributes to the high frequency of floods. On the western portion of the SU there is a shelf while to the east there is a deeper channel for water/sewer. This SU is a continuation of SU 1279

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets): 2

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Charcoal, shells

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by S. Lou, A.

Revised by CHM

PDFd by ECR

Entered by

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